

Dangote, the African Serial Entrepreneur

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to explore Dangote the African serial Entrepreneur Petroleum Refinery in Afrinca as is pleased to announce the commencement of a significant national initiative designed to transform Nigeria's fuel distribution landscape. Effective 15th of August 2025, the Refinery will begin the distribution of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) and diesel to marketers, petrol dealers, manufacturers, telecoms firms, aviation, and other large users across the country, with free logistics to boost distribution network. To ensure smooth take-off of this scheme, Dangote Refinery has invested in the procurement of 4,000 brand-new Compressed Natural Gas (CNG)-powered tankers. This phase of the programme will continue over an extended timeframe. The refinery is also investing in Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) stations, commonly referred to as daughter booster stations, supported by a fleet of over 100 CNG tankers across the country to ensure seamless product distribution. This strategic programme is part of the broader commitment to eliminating logistics costs, enhancing energy efficiency, promoting sustainability and supporting Nigeria's economic development. It affirms dedication to improving the availability and affordability of fuel, in support of broader efforts to strengthen the economy and improve the well-being of all Nigerians.

Key Words: *Dangote, African, Serial, Entrepreneur*

INTRODUCTION

Dangote Petroleum Refinery remains a proud partner in this national journey, a truly Nigerian company of global standards, dedicated to the well-being of all Nigerians. Under this initiative, all petrol stations purchasing PMS and diesel from the Dangote Petroleum Refinery will benefit from this enhanced logistics support. Key sectors such as manufacturing, telecommunications, and others will also gain from this transformative initiative, as reduced fuel costs will contribute to lower production costs, reduced inflation, and foster economic growth. Players in these key sectors and others can purchase directly from the Dangote Petroleum Refinery.

In addition, the refinery will offer a credit facility to those purchasing a minimum of 500,000 litres, allowing them to obtain an additional 500,000 litres on credit for two weeks, under bank guarantee. This pioneering effort marks a major milestone in the vision to revolutionise Nigeria's energy sector. Dangote Refinery is dedicated to ensuring that no place is left behind. The goal is to provide equitable access to affordable fuel for all Nigerians, regardless of location, making energy more accessible and sustainable for everyone, wherever they may be.

It is expected to revitalise previously inactive petrol stations, thereby driving job creation, stimulating small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), increasing government revenue, improving fuel access in rural and underserved communities, and strengthening investor confidence in Nigeria's downstream petroleum sector. This initiative is in line with the Renewed Hope Agenda of His Excellency, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, reflecting the shared commitment to economic progress, stability, and inclusive development. Marketers, petrol dealers, manufacturers, telecom companies, and all key stakeholders to embrace this landmark initiative.

According to Forbes magazine, the subsidiary produces 45.6 million metric tons of cement every year and operates in 10 African countries Dangote also owns the world's third-largest sugar refinery. As of March 31, 2021, Dangote Cement Group reported quarterly revenue of 332.7 billion Nigerian nairas, approximately US\$808.5 million As of April 2022, Aliko Dangote was the richest man in Africa. He had a net worth of nearly 15 billion U.S. dollars and ranked 130th worldwide; His Great Grand Father was the richest in West Africa.

Dangote Petroleum Refinery is set to begin the nationwide distribution of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) and diesel on August 15, 2025. This initiative involves deploying a fleet of 4,000 new Compressed Natural Gas (CNG)-powered tankers to deliver fuel directly to various users, including petrol stations, industrial firms, and other large consumers. The refinery aims to boost distribution and improve access to fuel across the country, with free logistics and generous credit facilities for large volume purchases.

After completing studies in business at Al-Azhar University, an Islamic institution in Cairo, in 1977, Dangote returned to Nigeria and was given a loan by his uncle to start a business,

which traded commodities and business supplies, primarily cement. By 1981 his firm was so successful that he had incorporated other businesses and established the Dangote Group. His empire extended to foodstuffs, including pasta, sugar, salt, and wheat; cement; haulage; and other concerns. Among his holdings were Dangote Industries Ltd., Dangote-Bail Nigeria, Ltd., Dangote Cement PLC, Benue Cement Company PLC, Dangote Sugar Refinery PLC, Dangote Flour Mills PLC, and Nascon Allied Industries PLC. In addition to its holdings in Nigeria, the Dangote Group has operations in several other African countries.

One of the most ambitious projects that Dangote was involved in was the construction of a massive oil refinery in Lagos State. He spearheaded the project in 2013 in an effort to solve the fuel crisis in Nigeria, which, despite being a leading oil-producing country, had to import most of the refined petroleum products it needed. At the same site Dangote also built a fertilizer plant and a power station. After several years of delays, the refinery the largest in all of Africa opened in May 2023, though it was not yet fully operational. It was anticipated that the refinery's production capacity of 650,000 barrels per day would significantly alter Nigeria's energy sector by eliminating the need for imported fuel while producing excess to export. In addition, the project generated an enormous number of temporary and permanent jobs during the construction phase and after completion.

Dangote's business success brought him great wealth. In 2008 he made his debut on *Forbes* magazine's annual list of billionaires in the world. In 2011, when *Forbes* launched its annual list of the 40 richest people in Africa, Dangote landed the top spot. Since then he has routinely ranked on both lists as well as in other, similar measures of wealth in Africa and in the world. In 2016 Dangote faced scrutiny when his name surfaced in the Panama Papers, which disclosed names of individuals who were linked to offshore shell companies. He was personally linked to 4 such companies, and his family and business associates were linked to at least 13. Dangote is well known for his humanitarian efforts. In 1994 the Dangote Foundation was incorporated for his philanthropic endeavours; it was renamed Aliko Dangote Foundation (ADF) in 2018. The foundation has focused much effort on addressing childhood malnutrition. It has also contributed toward efforts to combat viruses, such as those that cause polio, Ebola, and COVID-19. Moreover, the foundation has provided disaster relief.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Dangote Cement Company is a leading cement producing company in sub-Saharan Africa with existing operations in ten African countries. It is the market leader by capacity with a market share of 60.3% in terms of earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization. The company is able to maintain its market share leadership due to its strong market position and brand recognition, ownership of the largest production factory in SSA, large and extensive distribution network with specialized logistic apparatus, strong financial position and experienced and diverse workforce. It uses the advantages of backward integration and economies of scale to control the prices of cement in Nigeria and the other ten countries it operates.

Dangote cement Plc has a competitive advantage in West and Central Africa due to higher capacity utilization, duty free intra-regional trades, better foreign exchange operations and

lower raw material cost. It uses cost leadership strategy as the fulcrum of its overall sales and marketing principally based on strength, business integration and efficiency. The company's volume of. Abstract ©2023 | Published by Garden City Premier Business School, Port Harcourt-Nigeria sales/revenue showed consistent growth except for year 2019 because of Covid Pandemic. DANGCEM boasts of good financial health with low debt-to-asset ratio and net sales, operating profit, net income, and operating margin projections for the FY 2022, 2023 and 2024. The strategic decision to acquire two major cement manufacturing plants in Nigeria and the expansion into sub-Saharan markets was a masterstroke which helped to sustain the growth trajectory of the company as well as its projected profitability.

Aliko Dangote, the President and Chief Executive of the Pan-African conglomerate **Dangote Group**, has urged African business leaders to spearhead the transformation of the continent. During his address at the recently concluded African Renaissance Retreat in Kigali, Rwanda, Dangote emphasized that despite the numerous challenges facing Africa, the continent's youthful demographic and rich resources, comprising approximately 30% of the world's mineral reserves and the largest deposits of gold, cobalt, uranium, platinum, and diamonds, present significant opportunities for substantial and inclusive growth.

He remarked, "Moreover, Africa possesses 65% of the world's arable land and 10% of the planet's renewable freshwater resources. Collectively, these factors create a wealth of opportunities for dynamic, inclusive growth that leverages our vast human potential and natural resources to enhance prosperity, not only within Africa but globally." Dangote further noted that Africa stands at a pivotal moment, characterized by the youngest and fastest-growing population in the world, rapidly developing urban areas, and an increasing adoption of innovation and new technologies, including Artificial Intelligence.

Dangote highlighted that, despite facing numerous challenges such as visa issues, fluctuating government policies, a shortage of skilled labor, insufficient infrastructure, foreign exchange difficulties, inflation, high capital costs, and various conflicts, the Dangote Group has successfully expanded from Nigeria to 14 countries across Africa. The company operates in diverse sectors, including cement, fertilizers, sugar, oil refining, petrochemicals, and agriculture. "The encouraging news is that, in spite of these hurdles, we have managed to establish a pan-African Group that employs over 50,000 individuals and is projected to generate revenues exceeding \$30 billion by the end of 2025," he stated.

In initiating the retreat, Dangote expressed his long-standing desire to unite a group of committed African business leaders to confront the continent's challenges, devise practical solutions, and promote Africa as a promising investment hub despite its difficulties. He underscored that the retreat aimed to create a platform for collaborative efforts to address various pressing issues, including ongoing conflicts, energy and food security, supply chain challenges, the debt crisis, and the need for access to long-term concessional funding for development.

This intimate and high-level meeting aimed at addressing these critical issues and establishing a unified approach to shaping our development narrative is long overdue. With the continent's leading entrepreneurs, heads of major pan-African corporations, key figures from significant development institutions in Africa, our global institutional partners, prominent investors, influential civil society leaders, and several esteemed political figures,

this initial gathering will provide a platform for open and sincere discussions to identify our shared objectives, stated Dangote.

He further emphasized, "We are uniting not merely as representatives of our organizations but as innovators and drivers of change for our communities. It is our shared duty to contribute to the transformation of our continent. No one else will undertake this task for us, it is up to us, especially those present in this room." Dangote expressed optimism that the retreat would yield initiatives capable of significantly influencing Africa's future and enhancing the lives of its citizens. He recognized the valuable contributions of President Paul Kagame of Rwanda, former President Olusegun Obasanjo, former President Ellen Johnson Sirleaf, and former Prime Minister Hailemariam Dessalegn. Nonetheless, he emphasized the importance of transitioning from mere discussions to effective implementation that delivers real results.

The participants of the retreat committed to encouraging African private sector and political leaders to participate in ongoing high-level discussions. They proposed several initiatives, including advocating for the ratification of the free movement of people protocol, launching the African Renaissance Companies Gender Compact, and gathering prominent global business leaders of African descent. Additionally, the leaders sought to promote an initiative aimed at significantly lowering logistics costs across the continent and another focused on expanding internet access to a larger portion of Africa's population.

The retreat, held from September 6 to 8, featured notable participants such as Amina J. Mohammed, the Deputy Secretary-General of the United Nations; Prof. Benedict Oramah, the President and Chairman of the Board of Directors of the African Export-Import Bank; former Liberian President Ellen Johnson Sirleaf; Adebayo Ogunlesi, Chairperson of Global Infrastructure Partners; former Ethiopian Prime Minister Hailemariam Dessalegn; Samaila Zubairu from the African Finance Corporation; Makhtar Diop from the International Finance Corporation; and Jeremy Awori, the CEO of Ecobank Transnational Incorporated.

Nigeria's oil magnate and billionaire businessman, Aliko Dangote, says African entrepreneurs should be at the forefront of adding value to the continent's natural resources, to the benefit of the citizens. Dangote is in Namibia on an official business trip and paid a courtesy call on President Netumbo Nandi-Ndaitwah at State House. Sharing a brief of his success, the founder of the largest conglomerate in West Africa, including the Dangote Group and Refinery, believes African entrepreneurs are better placed to develop the continent. "There is no way anybody can come to develop our continent; the continent can only be developed by Africans, and that is why a company like ours has actually invested in 12 other African countries, not only Nigeria. Africa is Africa, and I know that our continent is very, very rich, but the natural resources and human resources can only be good when we put them to work. Natural resources under the ground can remain there forever if not harnessed, and that is why people like us, the entrepreneurs, must show the way to others that it is possible. We have actually done a heavy investment in East Africa, countries that were suffering from a lack of cement, in Tanzania, Zambia and South Africa."

Dangote also mentioned that the Dangote Group would continue to scout for business opportunities across the continent, in different areas of interest. President Nandi-Ndaitwah

reiterated that Africa's economic liberation requires that the citizens of the continent internalise their roles, especially local entrepreneurs. "We believe in Africa for Africans, particularly when it comes to our developmental agenda. We are saying no one else can liberate us economically but ourselves, and entrepreneurs are the ones we are looking at as citizens for us to move to the next level." The billionaire Nigerian businessman's official programme in Namibia would see him also visiting the Port of Walvis Bay, among other engagements.

Many awards and honors have been bestowed on Dangote over the years. In 2011 he was made a Grand Commander of the Order of the Niger (GCON), Nigeria's second highest honor, in recognition of his contributions to Nigeria's economic development. Other honours he has received include being made a Grand Commander of the National Order of the Republic of Benin (2013), a Commander of the National Order of Valour (2021) of Cameroon, and a Commander of the Order of Merit of Niger (2022).

Dangote Petroleum Refinery to Begin Distribution of PMS and Diesel Nationwide

Deploys 4,000 CNG Tankers to Enhance Distribution Network Nationwide, offer open to Marketers, Petrol Dealers, Manufacturers, Telecoms Firms, Aviation and other large users

DANGOTE PETROLEUM REFINERY TO DISTRIBUTE PMS AND DIESEL WITH FREE LOGISTICS NATIONWIDE

GR ...Deploys 4,000 CNG Tankers To Enhance Distribution Network Nationwide
GR ...Offer open to Marketers, Petrol Dealers, Manufacturers, Telecoms Firms, Aviation and other large users.

We sincerely thank His Excellency, Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu, President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, for his continued support, especially through the:

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Aliko Dangote, one of Africa's richest serial entrepreneurs, has called on his fellow business leaders to "take the lead in transforming the continent." Previously the continent's richest man, Dangote heads the vast Dangote Group conglomerate, which has interests in cement, trading, rice, and oil refining. The Dangote refinery, with a full capacity of 650,000 barrels per day, is meant to fulfil Nigeria's fuel needs but it has faced multiple issues since it began operations.

Dangote's commercial interests give him an outsized presence in West Africa's economy, among other regions it is present in. "With the foremost entrepreneurs on the continent, the leaders of the largest pan-African companies, those at the helm of the most important development institutions in Africa, our brothers and sisters leading global institutions, our leading investors, our pre-eminent civil society activists and a few of our most respected political leaders, this first step will be an opportunity to have a frank and honest dialogue amongst ourselves to consolidate what we see as our common ground," Dangote said at the recently concluded African Renaissance Retreat in Kigali, Rwanda.

Participants at the retreat also proposed to urge private and public sector leaders to have constant dialogue, urge the ratification of the free movement of people, and convene a top global business leaders of African descent, the Dangote Group said in a statement on Friday. Many longstanding plans crucial to the continent's economic development have stalled due to multiple reasons, slowing down transcontinental trade and economic cooperation.

Dangote's conglomerate employs over 50,000 people and generates revenues that the billionaire said should exceed \$30bn by the end of next year. In August, South African entrepreneur Johann Rupert (net worth: \$14.3bn) overtook Dangote (net worth: \$13.4bn) as the continent's wealthiest man according to the Bloomberg Billionaires Index. Rupert's company, Richemont, is the maker of luxury brands such as Cartier.

Nationwide Distribution:

The Dangote Petroleum Refinery will begin distributing PMS and diesel to marketers, petrol dealers, manufacturers, telecoms firms, aviation, and other large users across Nigeria starting August 15, 2025.

4,000 CNG-powered Tankers:

A significant part of this initiative involves deploying 4,000 new CNG-powered tankers to enhance delivery capacity and improve fuel access.

Impact on Distribution:

This initiative is expected to cut out traditional depot owners and intermediaries in the petroleum distribution chain, potentially leading to a more efficient and cost-effective delivery process.

Benefits for Consumers:

The refinery's efforts are expected to have a positive impact on fuel prices and supply, with potential benefits for consumers and various sectors of the economy.

Potential Monopoly Concerns:

There are ongoing discussions about potential market dominance issues and the need for transparency in logistics and market fairness as Dangote expands its distribution network.

Crude Oil Sourcing:

The refinery is also actively securing a steady supply of crude oil, including imports from international markets, to reach its full operational capacity of 650,000 barrels per day. Deploys 4,000 CNG Tankers to Enhance Distribution Network Nationwide. Offer open to Marketers, Petrol Dealers, Manufacturers, Telecoms Firms, Aviation and other large users. Dangote Petroleum Refinery is pleased to announce the commencement of a significant national initiative designed to transform Nigeria's fuel distribution landscape. Effective 15th of August 2025, the Refinery will begin the distribution of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) and diesel to marketers, petrol dealers, manufacturers, telecoms firms, aviation, and other large users across the country, with free logistics to boost distribution network.

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This initiative is in line with the Renewed Hope Agenda of His Excellency, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, reflecting our shared commitment to economic progress, stability, and inclusive development. We sincerely thank the Federal Government for its continued support, especially through the Naira-for-Crude scheme, which has helped stabilise fuel supply amid global price volatility. It marks a major revolution in the midstream and downstream sectors and stands as a key example of President Bola Tinubu's bold and reformative economic policies. We invite marketers, petrol dealers, manufacturers, telecom companies, and all key stakeholders to embrace this landmark initiative. The registration process, including Know Your Customer (KYC) verification, will take place from 16 June to 15 August, spanning a total of 60 days. Dangote Petroleum Refinery remains a proud partner in this national journey, a truly Nigerian company of global standards, dedicated to the well-being of all Nigerians.

Economic Policy Expert, Professor Ken Ife, has called on the Federal Government to urgently reform the Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority (NMDPRA). In an exclusive interview with correspondent in Abuja, Professor Ife accused

the agency of hindering Nigeria's economic growth and compromising consumer welfare. His comments follow growing calls by stakeholders for a review of the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021. Professor Ken stressed that the NMDPRA requires a complete overhaul to bring its operations in line with global best practices. He warned that without meaningful reform, Nigeria will continue to address symptoms while the root problems remain unresolved. He urged President Bola Tinubu to act swiftly and restructure the NMDPRA to stabilise the petroleum supply chain and restore public confidence.

This initiative will also make PMS more available nationwide, cutting off the need for hoarding. This level of price equalisation will cost Dangote Refinery nothing less than N200 billion, and invariably transferring subsidy from public sector to private sector. The argument that this initiative will create unemployment is false. Lower cost will be the underlying impact of this initiative (Prof. Ken Ife, Development Economist & Policy Expert 2025)

First set of NNPC trucks lift petrol at Dangote refinery

By Bunmi Aduloju

September 15, 2024

Dangote Petroleum Refinery says trucks owned by the Nigerian National Petroleum Company (NNPC) Limited have commenced loading premium motor spirit (PMS), also known as petrol, at its gantry.

Dangote Group shared videos on X showing the trucks stationed at the gantry on Sunday. "First set of trucks set for loading of PMS at the Dangote Petroleum Refinery," the company said. The development **followed** NNPC's deployment of trucks to the petrol-loading gantry of Dangote refinery on Saturday. "In preparation for the Dangote Refinery's scheduled petrol loading on Sunday, September 15, 2024, NNPC Ltd. has been mobilizing trucks to the refinery's fuel loading gantry in Ibeju-Lekki," NNPC said. On September 14, the federal government said Dangote refinery will **sell petrol to only the NNPC**, adding that interested marketers would have to buy the product from the national oil firm. However, the government said the Dangote refinery can sell diesel to any off-taker. Dangote refinery **commenced** petrol production on September 3.

On the same day, the Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority (NMDPRA) **said** the Dangote refinery is expected to supply 25 million litres of petrol daily in September and will subsequently increase the volume to 30 million litres daily from October.

The Federal Government sold crude oil valued at N219.38bn to the Dangote Petroleum Refinery in the first four months of 2025, The PUNCH reports. The government also earned \$1.59m from crude oil exports in April 2025, during the period it suspended sales of domestic crude allocations to the Dangote refinery and local refiners.

These details were contained in internal documents from the Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited, submitted at the Federation Account Allocation Committee meetings, and obtained by The PUNCH on Wednesday. The Federation Accounts Allocation Committee said a total revenue equivalent of N2.53bn was realised during the period, based on an average exchange rate of N1, 595.689 to the dollar, as provided by the Central Bank of Nigeria.

House of Reps to Investigate Crude Oil Theft

On March 19, the Dangote refinery suspended the sale of its petroleum products in naira due to a stalemate in the naira-for-crude deal between it and NNPC, which appeared to have failed. The 650,000 barrels per day capacity refinery lamented that there was a mismatch between its sales proceeds and its crude oil purchase obligations, which it said are currently denominated in US dollars.

“Dear valued customers, we wish to inform you that the Dangote Petroleum Refinery has temporarily halted the sale of petroleum products in Naira. This decision is necessary to avoid a mismatch between our sales proceeds and our crude oil purchase obligations, which are currently denominated in US dollars.

“To date, our sales of petroleum products in naira have exceeded the value of naira-denominated crude we have received. As a result, we must temporarily adjust our sales currency to align with our crude procurement currency,” the firm announced. During this period, the cost of loading petrol at private depots in Lagos jumped to above N900 per litre.

However, 21 days after the suspension, the Federal Executive Council officially ordered the full implementation of the naira-for-crude oil supply deal with local refiners. It stated that the initiative with local refineries is not a temporary measure, but a “key policy directive designed to support sustainable local refining.” The statement read, “The Technical Sub-Committee on the Crude and Refined Product Sales in Naira initiative convened an update meeting on Tuesday to review progress and address ongoing implementation matters.

“The stakeholders reaffirmed the government’s continued commitment to the full implementation of this strategic initiative, as directed by the Federal Executive Council.” Despite the directive, the Dangote refinery has continued to describe the crude allocation as inadequate, a situation it says has forced it to rely heavily on imports from the United States to sustain operations.

FINDINGS FROM THE REVIEWS

Findings by The PUNCH revealed that the government, through the Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited, sold crude worth N219.38bn to the 650,000-barrel-per-day Lagos-based refinery. The documents showed that nine cargoes were delivered to Dangote refinery, totaling 1,901,850 barrels sourced from the Okwuibome field operated by Sterling Oil Exploration & Energy Production Company under Production Sharing Contracts and the Nigerian Agip Exploration. The crude was sold at unit prices ranging from \$74.87 to \$80.34 per barrel, using exchange rates between N1,501.22/\$ and N1,562.91/\$.

One of the documents seen by The PUNCH read, “The Dangote domestic lifting is payable in naira based on Afrexim Bank advised exchange rate.” A monthly breakdown showed that crude oil supply from the government to the refinery surged by over 538 per cent between January and April 2025. An analysis of official figures showed that crude sales to the Lagos-based refinery stood at N17.52bn in January, rising steadily by 88 per cent to N32.95bn in February, then by 73 per cent to N56.97bn in March, and spiking by 96.4 per cent to a record N111.95bn in April.

While crude oil supply to the refinery surged to N219.38bn between January and April 2025, fresh findings by The PUNCH show that the Federal Government earned a total of N231.47bn from crude exports to foreign buyers within the same period. Dangote plans to list Africa’s largest oil refinery in 2026 to quell monopoly fears. Dangote's decision to move forward with the listings of the oil and fertilizer refinery reflects the conglomerate’s broader strategy to attract new investors and unlock greater value for shareholders. Aliko Dangote plans to list his Nigerian oil refinery on the stock market by the end of 2026. The Group also plans to list its urea fertilizer plant, producing 2.8 million tons annually, by the end of this year. The \$20 billion Dangote Refinery, inaugurated in 2024, is Africa's largest with a processing capacity of 650,000 barrels daily.

Aliko Dangote, Africa’s richest man, has announced plans to list his massive Nigerian oil refinery on the stock market by the end of 2026, aiming to expand its investor base and ease concerns about monopoly power. Speaking at the African Export-Import Bank’s annual general meeting in Abuja, Dangote also revealed that the Dangote Group will proceed with the stock market listing of its urea fertilizer plant, capable of producing 2.8 million tons annually, before the end of this year.

Back in July, Dangote announced plans to list both the fertilizer and petrochemical divisions of the Dangote Refinery in the first quarter of 2025. The decision to move forward with the listings reflects the conglomerate’s broader strategy to attract new investors and unlock greater value for shareholders. He also revealed plans for a dual listing of the refinery on both the London and Lagos stock exchanges. The \$20 billion refinery, began operations in 2024 and is the largest on the African continent, with a capacity to process 650,000 barrels of crude oil per day. Ranked by Bloomberg as having a higher capacity than the ten largest refineries in Europe, the refinery currently produces aviation fuel, diesel, gasoline, and naphtha.

CONCLUSION

Dangote Petroleum Refinery and Petrochemicals is a 650,000 barrels per day (BPD) integrated refinery located in the Lekki Free Zone of Ibeju Lekki Lagos, Nigeria. It is

Africa's biggest oil refinery and the world's biggest single-train facility. The Pipeline Infrastructure at the Dangote Petroleum Refinery is the largest anywhere in the world, with 1,100 kilometers to handle 3 Billion Standard Cubic Foot of gas per day. The Refinery alone has a 435MW Power Plant that can meet the total power requirement of Ibadan DisCo.

The Refinery will meet 100% of the Nigerian requirement of all refined products and also have a surplus of each of these products for export. Dangote Petroleum Refinery is a multi-billion-dollar project that will create a market for \$21 Billion per annum of Nigerian Crude. It is designed to process Nigerian crude with the ability to also process other crudes.

The fact that Dangote Cement has been able to expand its cement production business across several African states, where its political influence is less certain, is also evidence that closeness to government is not the only explanation for the Dangote success story. In this direction, the company has either completed or is in the process of building cement production plants in Cameroon, Ethiopia, Republic of Congo, Liberia, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Kenya, Zambia, Ivory Coast and Ghana. The company is also building an import/packaging facility in Sierra Leone (Dangote Cement 2014 Annual Report).

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